

Mapping and characterizing global mobility infrastructures and its associated resource use and GHG emissions

Dominik Wiedenhofer^{1,*}, André Baumgart^{1,x}, Sarah Matej^{1,x}, Doris Virág¹, Gerald Kalt¹, Maud Lanau²,
Danielle Densley Tingley², Zhiwei Liu³, Jing Guo⁴, Hiroki Tanikawa³, Helmut Haberl¹

¹ University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna.

² Department of Civil and Structural Engineering, University of Sheffield, UK.

³ Graduate School of Environmental Studies, Nagoya University, Nagoya 464-8601, Japan.

⁴ Institute of Urban Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Xiamen 361021, China.

X ... shared second authors.

* ... corresponding author: Dominik.wiedenhofer@boku.ac.at
[University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna \(BOKU\)](#)
[Department of Economics and Social Sciences](#)
[Institute of Social Ecology \(SEC\)](#)
[Schottenfeldgasse 29, 1070 Vienna](#)
[Austria](#)

Highlights

- Scope: 18 infrastructure types, 8 bulk materials and cradle to gate GHG emissions
- Global mapping reveals large differences in stock intensity per capita and area
- Income and population density shape infrastructure stock levels
- Scaling catch-up scenarios by population density yields lower stock-flow estimates

29 **Abstract**

30 Road and rail infrastructures are the physical foundation for mobility services, but also induce
31 substantial resource use and GHG emissions. The resource-efficient provision of sufficient
32 infrastructures hence amounts to a global sustainability challenge. However, little is known about the
33 scale and patterns of already accumulated stocks of infrastructure networks globally, the resources
34 and emissions required for construction and maintenance, as well as the potentials of settlement and
35 population density to save required infrastructures.

36 Herein, we present a mapping and modelling of materials stocked in mobility infrastructures and the
37 associated material flows and life cycle GHG emissions, for 180 countries in 2021 and at a spatial
38 resolution of 5 arcminutes. We combine crowd-sourced Open Street Maps data with a global dataset
39 on infrastructure designs, material compositions, lifetimes and network growth rates to derive stocks
40 and flows, incl. a density-scaled catch-up scenario.

41 We find that 313 Gt, or 42 tons/cap are stocked in global mobility infrastructures, the majority being
42 aggregate and asphalt. Stocks are highly unequally distributed between and within countries, from 21-
43 102 tons/cap between low versus high income countries; to a factor 10^1 - 10^4 difference in stock
44 intensity between rural, suburban and dense urban areas. Construction uses 8.4 Gt/year of materials,
45 causing 0.4 Gt CO₂eq/year of life cycle emissions. Two-thirds of these flows are locked-in for
46 maintaining and replacing existing stocks. For future stock catch-up levels, we expect substantial
47 resource use and life cycle emissions, but also large potential savings from dense(r) settlements.

48 In summary, mobility infrastructures amount to 1/3 of total global societal material stocks, requiring
49 10% of resource use and causing 1% of GHG emissions globally, excl. mobility itself. Stock catch-up
50 could require 1.6-7.4% of the carbon budgets for stabilizing climate heating at 1.5-2°C. Supply- and
51 demand-side measures seem necessary to avoid future GHG emissions and impacts from resource use.

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53 **Keywords:** material and energy flow analysis (MEFA); socio-economic metabolism; transport; road;
54 rail;

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56 1. Introduction

57 Networks of mobility infrastructures provide the physical basis for safe and affordable access to
58 mobility, connecting settlements and cities and enabling land-uses around the world. These
59 infrastructures enable growing mobility and transport, which directly causes 15% of global GHG
60 emissions (Lamb et al., 2021). While the worldwide demand for mobility is expected to increase
61 substantially (European Commission. Joint Research Centre, 2019), rapid and deep decarbonization via
62 supply- and demand-side measures are required to achieve climate change mitigation targets (Lamb
63 et al., 2021). However, there is also a lack of access to reliable and sustainable mobility infrastructures
64 and subsequent mobility services in many places, as enshrined in SDG 9.1 (Virág et al., 2022; Wenz et
65 al., 2020). The resource efficient provision of sufficient mobility infrastructure hence amounts to a
66 global sustainability challenge.

67 Currently, more than half of global resource extraction is used to construct and maintain growing
68 societal material stocks around the world (Krausmann et al., 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2021), causing
69 25-35% of global GHG emissions directly and indirectly during industrial materials extraction,
70 processing and construction (Hertwich, 2021; Lamb et al., 2021). Socio-economic material stocks
71 constitute the biophysical basis of almost all socio-economic activities: material stocks and resource
72 flows jointly provide “functions” and “services” (Kalt et al., 2019), e.g. via mobility and transport, well-
73 tempered and -lit living space, water, food and energy supply, etc. (Fisch-Romito, 2021; Lin et al., 2017;
74 Pauliuk and Hertwich, 2015). These systemic interrelations have been conceptualized as *stock-flow-*
75 *service nexus* (Haberl et al., 2017, 2021a), where the demand for functions and services is intertwined
76 and locked in by existing stocks, which in turn jointly drive resource use and emissions. Future
77 trajectories of stock expansion and resulting GHG emissions for build-up and service provision are
78 therefore a key challenge for more sustainable resource use and climate change mitigation (Creutzig
79 et al., 2021; Fisch-Romito, 2021; Krausmann et al., 2020; Müller et al., 2013; Tanikawa et al., 2021).

80 Herein, we investigate global material stocks and flows of materials and emissions due to mobility
81 infrastructure networks around the world, complementing and combining previous research lines
82 which revolve around life cycle assessments (LCA) of infrastructure construction, resource efficiency
83 and circularity (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019), as well as the emerging
84 issue of modelling and mapping infrastructure stocks at the network level across spatiotemporal scales
85 (Fu et al., 2021; Lanau et al., 2019). We herein deliberately exclude mobility modes and services, as
86 well as transport poverty and decent mobility standards (Jeyaseelan et al., 2022; Lowans et al., 2021;
87 Virág et al., 2022), rather focusing on characterizing and mapping global material stocks in mobility
88 infrastructure networks, their patterns and subsequent resource use and emissions globally.

89 Several important findings emerge from previous work, which we build upon herein. Firstly, local
90 transport of materials, construction activity, as well as energy and emissions during material recovery
91 activities are usually seen as minor contributors to overall life cycle emissions from constructing and
92 maintaining infrastructure (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019). However,
93 systematic reviews of hundreds of LCA case studies also showed that most work lacks crucial
94 documentation of infrastructure design parameters and inventory data, uses inconsistent modeling
95 approaches, and often lacks clear system boundaries, all of which renders these results non-
96 reproducible and limits their value for cumulative research (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019;
97 Olugbenga et al., 2019). Recommended future research includes modelling of infrastructure at the
98 level of entire infrastructure networks across spatio-temporal scales as presented herein, as well as
99 more systematic coverage of all life cycle stages, transparent methods and data (AzariJafari et al., 2016;
100 Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019). Along these lines of suggested
101 improvements, (Wenz et al., 2020) modelled the life cycle emissions required to provide quasi-
102 universal access to all-season mobility infrastructures globally, mainly via paved roads in proximity to
103 settlements, showing that tackling this glaring insufficiency and under-provision with infrastructures
104 could cause only minor GHG emissions.

105 Studies at the network-level, from national to global scales, often use dynamic material and energy
106 flow analysis (MEFA) to investigate material stocks and flows of socio-economic systems (Haberl et al.,
107 2019; Lanau et al., 2019). For example, studies explored how much material stock, as well as material
108 flows and emissions are associated with mobility infrastructure across spatiotemporal scales, for
109 example for European road and railway networks (Wiedenhofer et al., 2015), for Japanese stock
110 evolution (Tanikawa et al., 2021, 2015), for urbanization and transport infrastructure dynamics in
111 Vietnam (Miatto et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2018), for global subway networks (Mao et al., 2021), the
112 USA road network (AzariJafari et al., 2021; Miatto et al., 2017), for islands (Noll et al., 2019) and for a
113 growing number of cities and urban areas (Gassner et al., 2020; Guo et al., 2014; Lanau and Liu, 2020;
114 Virág et al., 2021). These studies showed that mobility infrastructure stocks constitute a major share
115 of national socio-economic material stocks, that they require substantial amounts of resources and
116 emissions and that they constitute materialized path-dependencies regarding (future) requirements
117 for maintenance and replacements.

118 Increasingly, remote-sensing and crowd-sourced data are used to complement official statistics and
119 census data, overcoming some of their limitations regarding network-level coverage, completeness
120 and data availability around the world (Haberl et al., 2021b; Moran et al., 2020; Wenz et al., 2020). For
121 example, the Global Roads Inventory Project compiled a harmonized mapping of road network types
122 and lengths around the world, combining official statistics and crowd-sourced information, but

123 excluding a large amount of unspecified and unclear roads, esp. regarding local or rural roads (Meijer
124 et al., 2018). (Barrington-Leigh and Millard-Ball, 2017) showed that the Open Street Maps Directory
125 (OSM) is more than 80% complete globally, providing the most comprehensive coverage of
126 infrastructure networks lengths and types globally. A number of spatially-explicit studies of material
127 stocks and flows for mobility infrastructures has begun utilizing these novel sources (Haberl et al.,
128 2021b; Klooststra et al., 2022; Lanau and Liu, 2020; Tanikawa et al., 2015; Virág et al., 2021; Wenz et al.,
129 2020). Recently, (Virág et al., 2022) presented country-level estimates of infrastructure stocks using
130 OSM and material compositions data, to explore how much infrastructure might be required to
131 support decent mobility for all. While these studies provided important insights, a systematic global
132 mapping and modelling of infrastructure networks and their physical stocks, flows and patterns is
133 missing.

134 In this article, we present four novel contributions:

- 135 1) *How much material stocks of mobility infrastructures are there and how are they distributed*
136 *around the world?*
- 137 2) *What are the spatial patterns of infrastructure stocks, esp. in relation to population density?*
- 138 3) *Which yearly flows of materials and GHG emissions are associated with maintenance,*
139 *replacement and expansion of mobility infrastructure stocks?*
- 140 4) *What are the material and emissions implications of a hypothetical global catch-up and*
141 *convergence of global infrastructure stocks, considering current population density patterns?*

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143 In the following, we present our system definition, methods, data, assumptions and previous work we
144 are building on. Section 3 presents global results on stocks, patterns and flows. Section 4 discusses the
145 implications of these results vis a vis global resource use and climate change mitigation, their
146 limitations, as well as promising next steps, before section 5 concludes. The supplementary
147 information provides further documentation and validation of results and the supplementary data
148 contains all results.

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151 **2. Methods and data**

152 The aim of this modelling is to characterize and map material stocks contained in mobility
 153 infrastructure networks around the world, and to derive estimates of resource use and emissions
 154 associated with the expansion and maintenance of those stocks. We deliberately exclude mobility
 155 services themselves and focus on its infrastructural basis. For this purpose, we utilize a stock-driven,
 156 dynamic material and energy/emissions flows modelling for 180 countries for the year ~2021, drawing
 157 on spatially-explicit data on mobility infrastructures from Open Street Maps (OSM) at 5 arcmin, a
 158 harmonized dataset on infrastructure designs, material intensities, typical lifetimes per infrastructure
 159 to deduct flows, as well as cradle-to-gate LCA factors of the GHG emissions of materials production
 160 (Figure 1). Spatially-explicit networks of 18 infrastructure types are derived from crowd-sourced Open
 161 Street Maps information (Geofabrik, 2022) and (OurAirports, 2021), utilizing algorithms for data
 162 processing, as well as classifications and procedures developed and documented in detail previously
 163 (Haberl et al., 2021b; Virág et al., 2022). We then developed a global dataset on infrastructure widths
 164 and material intensities per type of infrastructure, to estimate material stocks and flows for the year
 165 ~2021. Compared to previous work by (Virág et al., 2022), who presented country-level total stock
 166 estimates, we here expand our coverage of countries, map and analyze stock patterns, derive flows of
 167 materials and GHG emissions currently, and model a scenario considering relations to population
 168 density. For the analysis, the (World Bank, 2021) classification of countries into four income groups
 169 were utilized. A supplementary data file for this article reports on all countries, their groupings, as well
 170 as the material stock-flow and GHG results.

System overview:

Scope:

- 18 road- and rail-based infrastructure types, incl. tunnels & bridges
- 8 bulk material stocks and flows
- Cradle-to-gate CO₂eq life-cycle emissions
- 180 countries, in the year ~2021
- Global mapping at 5 arcminutes (~9x9km²)

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 172 Figure 1: System overview and scope of the analysis. Please note that materials transportation, construction, use of stocks by
 173 mobility itself, and end-of-life phases are excluded from the energy and emissions life cycle factors. **[One column wide figure]**

174 In a stock-driven modelling as presented herein, material stocks MS are estimated by multiplying
 175 infrastructure network lengths L , with their respective widths w and material intensities MI (mass of
 176 materials per m²), for each infrastructure type st , material m , country c and year t (Equation 1).

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$$MS_{st,m,c,t} = L_{st,c,t} * w_{st,c} * MI_{st,m,c} \quad \text{Eq.1.}$$

178 Material flows due to expansion of infrastructure networks are derived by estimating how much
 179 infrastructure was newly built, approximated by applying suitable growth rates g (see below for how
 180 they were estimated) to the existing infrastructure network $L * w$ (Equation 2).

$$181 \quad \text{Expansion}_{st,m,c,t} = (L_{st,c,t} * W_{st,c}) * g_{st,c,t} * MI_{st,m,c} \quad \text{EQ.2}$$

182 Material flows for maintenance and replacements of stocks can be derived in a first approximation by
 183 assuming a steady “leaching” lifetime model (van der Voet et al., 2002; Wiedenhofer et al., 2015). Such
 184 a leaching model simplifies real-world dynamics of stock demolition and replacement which are
 185 shaped by age-type-cohort ageing dynamics, as well as other socio-ecological influences, such as
 186 available monetary budgets for repairs and maintenance, COVID-19 induced temporary shocks, other
 187 socio-political reasons for stock-building or demolition, or damages to infrastructures due to natural
 188 events, local ground and/or weather conditions, etc. However, due to data limitations, the leaching
 189 lifetime model is the only feasible one, and yields a first approximation of the range of material flows
 190 to be expected. To model maintenance and replacements, we estimate how much of the infrastructure
 191 length L remains from the year before by deducting the newly added length ($L * g$, see Eq. 1), and
 192 utilize the remaining length to approximate maintenance and replacement requirements, given
 193 average service lifetimes LT and the material intensities MI of those respective infrastructures st
 194 (Equation 3).

$$195 \quad \text{Maintenance}_{st,m,c,t} = \left((L_{st,c,t} - (L_{st,c,t} * g_{st,c,t})) * w_{st,c} \right) * 1/LT_{st,m} * MI_{st,m,c} \quad \text{EQ.3}$$

196 Finally, for these material flows, the associated lifecycle energy requirements LCA_{EI} and life cycle
 197 carbon emissions LCA_{GHG} are estimated (Equations 4 & 5).

$$198 \quad \text{Energy}_{c,t} = \sum (\text{Maintenance}_{st,m,c,t} + \text{Expansion}_{st,m,c,t}) * LCA_{EI_{m,c,t}} \quad \text{EQ.4.}$$

$$199 \quad \text{CO}_2eq_{c,t} = \sum (\text{Maintenance}_{st,m,c,t} + \text{Expansion}_{st,m,c,t}) * LCA_{GHG_{m,c,t}} \quad \text{EQ.5.}$$

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203 2.1. Data on mobility infrastructure types, lengths and material compositions

204 We use crowd-sourced information on global mobility infrastructure lengths from OSM, considering
 205 33 detailed OSM data keys as well as information on airport runway pavement types and lengths from
 206 OurAirports, to derive a comprehensive and spatially-explicit dataset on infrastructure network
 207 lengths for 180 countries. We aggregate the 33 detailed OSM categories into the following 18
 208 infrastructure types: six road types (motorway, primary, secondary, tertiary, local, and rural), five rail-
 209 based infrastructure types (railways, underground, elevated and ground-level subway, and tram and
 210 others), as well as all road and railway bridges and tunnels identified in OSM, as well as airport
 211 runways, building on OSM processing procedures developed previously (Haberl et al., 2021b).

212 We compiled data on infrastructure widths and material intensities for 8 materials and 18
213 infrastructure types, from a variety of peer-reviewed sources as well as national construction
214 guidelines and infrastructure design manuals (Table 1). We include asphalt, concrete, aggregates (sand
215 & gravel), timber, iron/steel, aluminum, copper, and other metals. Those materials make up the socio-
216 economic material stocks of all 18 infrastructure types following consistent and transparent system
217 boundaries (see supplementary information for further documentation and drawings). For roads we
218 include the asphalt and concrete top layers as well as the base layers primarily consisting of aggregates,
219 however excluding the subgrade consisting mainly of compressed local earth. For railways we include
220 the metal rails and sleeper plates, the wooden or concrete sleepers, as well as the ballast layers of
221 aggregate. Material intensity factors for tunnels and bridges only cover the load-bearing structure
222 itself, excluding the road or rail running on top or through it; roads and railways in tunnels and on
223 bridges are estimated with infrastructure specific material intensities.

224 A harmonized compilation of previous studies where sufficient information was available to re-use
225 data shows relatively good agreement per infrastructure type (table 1). However, not enough
226 datapoints/studies were available to robustly assign specific intensities to locally/regionally specific
227 conditions, countries or even world-regions; the main differentiation we can robustly apply are, that
228 roads in the USA are significantly wider than anywhere else. While a large number of LCA studies for
229 roads and other mobility infrastructure are available, they often focus on material mixes in different
230 road constructions technologies, e.g. asphalt (flexible) vs concrete (rigid), and usually do not report
231 crucial design parameters such as widths or road type, inhibiting reproducibility and re-usability (Hoxha
232 et al., 2021; Olugbenga et al., 2019). As most road statistics, legal construction guidelines, as well as
233 the crowd-sourced OSM information used herein is structured along road types themselves – e.g.
234 kilometers of motorways or local roads, only a limited number of studies could be used to derive
235 material intensities per infrastructure types. In order to not cause variation in results across countries
236 which are solely driven by small differences in the limited number of underlying studies, we therefore
237 opted for global “typical” material intensities per infrastructure type. Only for a handful of countries
238 nationally specific material intensities could be sourced, e.g., Germany and Austria (Haberl et al.,
239 2021b), the UK, the USA, Japan and China (Table 1).

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244 *Table 1: Overview of the material intensities per infrastructure types utilized in this study. Iron/steel, aluminum, copper and*
245 *timber are shown as “other materials*”, although they are separately modelled and reported in the supplementary material.*
246 *Bold numbers show the global averages as used herein, while the numbers in brackets indicate minima and maxima across*

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the utilized sources. Please note that for Germany, Austria, the UK, the USA, Japan and China, country-specific material intensities were developed. Material intensities for bridges and tunnels cover only the load bearing structure, while the road surface or railway tracks are estimated separately. We refer to the supplementary information for more details.

Infrastructure type		Global material intensities [t/m ²]				Data sources	
		Asphalt	Aggregate	Concrete ^a	Other materials*		Total
Roads	Motorway	0.47 [0.14-1.17]	1.26 [0.76-1.77]	– [0.00-0.25]	–	1.73 [1.12-2.94]	(Alzaim et al., 2020; Alzard et al., 2019; Bai et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2017; CSIR, 2000; DMR, 2014; DMT, 2016; Fishman et al., in preparation; Frantz et al., submitted; Haberl et al., 2021b; Henderson and van Zyl, 2017; Özgenel, 2016; Tanikawa et al., 2015; Wiedenhofer et al., in preparation)
	Primary	0.38 [0.11-0.76]	1.06 [0.65-1.52]	– [0.00-0.30]	–	1.43 [0.79-2.28]	
	Secondary	0.33 [0.08-0.68]	0.96 [0.54-1.15]	– [0.00-0.28]	–	1.30 [0.76-1.84]	
	Tertiary	0.26 [0.04-0.60]	0.86 [0.41-1.02]	– [0.00-0.39]	–	1.12 [0.58-1.62]	
	Local ^b	0.09 [0.04-0.30]	0.41 [0.09-0.97]	– [0.00-0.25]	–	0.50 [0.35-1.25]	
	Rural ^c	0.04 [0.00-0.21]	0.26 [0.15-0.54]	– [0.00-0.03]	–	0.30 [0.26-0.75]	
	Motorway bridge	–	–	1.18 [0.11-1.53]	0.14 [0.12-0.21]	1.32 [0.22-1.75]	(Fishman et al., in preparation; Haberl et al., 2021b; Tanikawa et al., 2015; Watt, 2019; Wiedenhofer et al., in preparation)
	Other road bridge	–	–	1.00 [0.11-1.30]	0.16 [0.14-0.21]	1.15 [0.24-1.51]	
	Road tunnel	–	–	2.80 [0.56-4.56]	0.12 [0.10-0.17]	2.92 [0.66-4.73]	
	Runway (flexible)	0.28	0.69	–	–	0.97	(Federal Aviation Administration, 2016; Haberl et al., 2021b)
Runway (rigid)	–	0.69	0.37	–	1.06		
Railway	Railway	–	0.35 [0.24-0.81]	0.03 [0.00-0.04]	0.03 [0.02-0.04]	0.41 [0.27-0.85]	(Fishman et al., in preparation; Frantz et al., submitted; Haberl et al., 2021b; Tanikawa et al., 2015; Wiedenhofer et al., in preparation)
	Railway bridge	–	–	0.51 [0.12-1.67]	1.12 [0.10-1.46]	1.62 [0.22-3.12]	
	Railway tunnel	–	–	4.14 [3.37-5.04]	0.12 [0.05-0.15]	4.26 [3.43-5.19]	
	Subway underground	–	0.65 [0.00-2.61]	10.00 [0.42-13.19]	0.55 [0.25-0.66]	11.20 [0.67-16.45]	
	Subway elevated	–	0.49 [0.43-0.67]	3.49 [0.11-4.61]	0.28 [0.02-0.36]	4.25 [0.55-5.65]	
	Subway ground-level	–	0.49 [0.43-0.67]	1.78 [0.11-2.34]	0.20 [0.02-0.26]	2.46 [0.55-3.26]	
	Tram/other	–	0.03 [0.00-0.04]	0.42 [0.00-0.56]	0.02 [0.02-0.03]	0.47 [0.03-0.62]	

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^a Concrete in roads is assumed to be used only in the USA and China due to lack of information for other countries. ^b For the local road MI we assume that 50% are paved and 50% are unpaved; where only 25% of these unpaved roads are considered as gravel roads, whereas 75% are assumed to be compacted local earth, which have a material intensity of zero. ^c The rural road MI is weighted at the national level based on shares of each OSM track key length in total track length, where the first track key is assumed to be asphalted while the remaining track keys are assumed to be 50% gravel and 50% compacted local earth roads.

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258 2.2. OSM processing and mapping of infrastructure types

259 OSM data was downloaded from (Geofabrik, 2022) as PBF files per country, or in some cases per
260 country group when individual countries were not available, e.g. for the Gulf Cooperation Council.
261 Using Python 3.8.10. and the Pyrosm library (<https://pyrosm.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>), road and
262 railway networks were extracted for 33 different OSM classes and aggregated into 8 different
263 infrastructure types. National boundaries were clipped with shapefiles from EUROSTAT to avoid
264 overlap in border regions. To arrive at a global mapping of material stocks at 5 arcmin resolution, the
265 length of each infrastructure category within a grid cell was calculated and multiplied with the
266 corresponding widths and material intensities. Land area and population density from HYDE 3.2.1.
267 (Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017) were used to calculate material stocks intensity of infrastructure per
268 square kilometer and per capita within each grid cell.

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270 2.3. Deriving material flows and life-cycle emissions for the maintenance and 271 expansion of infrastructure stocks

272 Stock growth rates are utilized to derive a first approximation of material flows resulting from
273 infrastructure expansion (see Eq. 3). This approach is used because international time series
274 information on the development of infrastructure networks is incomplete and unreliable, as evidenced
275 by the fact that four major international data sources yield conflicting levels and trends, see
276 supplementary information section 4, summarizing data from (European Commission, 2020; Eurostat,
277 2021a, 2021b; OECD, 2021; UNECE, 2021a, 2021b). Even after substantial efforts at harmonization and
278 data cleaning, as documented in the supplementary information, no robust trend information could
279 be derived. In summary, it seems that growth rates fluctuate between 0 – 2%/year. Therefore, to
280 derive a first approximation of reasonable ranges of global material flows, we calculate three variants
281 by assuming the following growth rates: for the upper-middle- and high-income countries, we calculate
282 low growth with +0.5%/year, intermediate with +1%/year and high with +2%/year. For the low-income
283 and lower-middle income countries we halved those growth rates, i.e., use +0.25%/year for low,
284 +0.5%/year for middle and +1%/year for the high growth variant.

285 Average service lifetimes per infrastructure types and materials are used to estimate maintenance and
286 replacement flows (see Eq. 4), which are derived from the literature, a recent systematic review of
287 road LCA studies (Hoxha et al., 2021), direct communication with experts, and own assumptions (Table
288 2). To again derive ranges of yearly material flows, we assume $\pm 30\%$ deviations from the ‘best guess’
289 estimates.

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291 Table 2: Overview of service lifetimes assumptions life cycle emissions data utilized. Service lifetimes are applied by
 292 infrastructure type and material, with mean lifetimes shown. As sensitivity testing, we also model $\pm 30\%$ min/max ranges. For
 293 life cycle emissions data, mean, as well as min/max by world-regions are utilized (see below and supplementary information).
 294 Bold numbers indicate mean modeling parameter values, while the numbers in brackets indicate min/max values.

Material	Lifetime [years]			Life cycle emissions [tCO ₂ e/t]
	Roads and runways	Railways and trams	Bridges, tunnels, subways ^c	Cradle-to-gate life cycle emissions of materials production
Asphalt	12 ^a and 29	–	–	0.046 [0.038–0.065]
Aggregates	120	120	120	0.004 [0.001–0.008]
Concrete	33	50	120	^b 0.709 [0.543–0.891]
Iron/steel	–	30	120	2.147 [1.874–2.531]
Aluminum	–	50	120	9.789 [6.197–14.237]
Copper	–	50	120	4.271 [2.405–6.354]
Timber	–	50	–	0.295 [0.249–0.400]
Other	–	50	120	–
Data sources	(Hoxha et al., 2021)	(UIC, 2016)	(Watt, 2019)	See supplementary information section 4

295 ^a The upper most asphalt wearing course in roads is modelled to be replaced every 12 years (Hoxha et al., 2021).

296 ^b Life cycle emissions factors for cement content of concrete.

297 ^c These lifetimes only relate to the load bearing structural parts; the roads/rails contained are modelled separately.

298 To assess the life cycle energy and GHG implications of global mobility infrastructure stocks and related
 299 material flows, we summarize literature values and information from LCA databases to arrive at energy
 300 & GHG lifecycle information for materials production and recycling (Table 2 and supplementary
 301 information section 3). A comprehensive literature review for energy and greenhouse gas (GHG)
 302 intensities of the considered materials was performed. The main processes and influencing factors on
 303 current and future energy/GHG intensities as well as data sources/publications that appear as
 304 particularly useful/reliable are identified. Existing reviews about LCAs of infrastructure construction
 305 were consulted (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019). Data referring to
 306 historical years in the timeframe 2010-2020 are adopted for the respective reference year(s) and
 307 country/region. GHG intensities for countries or regions not available from literature are derived from
 308 region-specific CO₂ intensities of final energy and/or electricity supply, depending on whether the
 309 respective industrial processes are primarily based on fuels or electricity¹. We refer to the
 310 supplementary information section 3 for a more detailed documentation.

311 The scope of the summarized lifecycle energy and emissions data largely follows “cradle-to-gate”
 312 system boundaries (LCA stages A1 to A3). Not considered processes are transport to the site,
 313 construction, the use phase (excluding traffic emissions or carbonation of concrete), demolition, as

¹ Non-CO₂ greenhouse gases are disregarded in this context, due to their small relevance in the context of energy generation.

314 well as collection for reuse, which are usually considered as minor contributors to overall life cycle
315 emissions (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019). A notable exception is
316 asphalt, where the data refers to laid material, including transport and construction (i.e. LCA stages A1
317 to A5). Energy intensities refer to final energy, i.e. fuels and electricity consumed by the respective
318 industries. CO₂ as well as any other greenhouse gases reported in the summarized literature are
319 considered; the unit of GHG intensities is thus tons of CO₂-equivalents (t CO₂e). The intensities
320 summarized in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.** and shown in the subsequent
321 figures therefore all refer to final energy and GHG emissions per material flow.

322 Since most studies report only aggregated GHG emissions and usually do not provide full
323 documentation of their lifecycle inventories, incl. clear system boundaries and all assumptions, it was
324 not possible to correct for eventual inconsistencies in scopes, for example due to different underlying
325 inclusions/exclusions of flows & processes (supply chain truncations), different global warming
326 potentials of non-CO₂ emissions, or diverging coverage of GHGs. However, we assume that this
327 methodological deficiency causes only minor errors that are negligible in the present context.

328 2.4 Modelling a catch-up and convergence scenario

329 The aim of this scenario is to model a population density dependent, hypothetically instantaneous
330 catch-up of infrastructure stock levels in all countries to those stock levels found in high income
331 nations. For this purpose, we start from the significant differences in stock intensity for different
332 population densities observed between world regions at ~10x10km² raster cells (Figure 4). The
333 scenario is then calculated per infrastructure type and material stock, based on gridded population
334 density for the year 2017 from HYDE 3.2.1. (Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017). We model a hypothetical
335 catch-up of all countries to the stock levels per capita and per unit area found in high-income countries.
336 We used highly detailed population density bins to capture gradients of stock intensity, starting with
337 below 1 cap/km², in steps of 5 cap/km² from 5 to 50, in steps of 10 from 50 to 1,000, in steps of
338 100cap/km² from 1,000 to 4,000, in steps of 500 from 4,000 to 10,000 and in steps of 2,000 cap/km²
339 from 10,000 to 20,000, with one last bin containing all cells with population densities above 20,000
340 cap/km².

341 For each population density bin, we calculated the average stock per infrastructure type, across all
342 raster cells in high-income countries, and applied this value to the cells in all other countries which fall
343 within the same population density bin. The average was chosen over the median, because at lower
344 population densities most of the cells, especially for some infrastructure types like motorways, contain
345 zero stocks/cap, which does not represent the overall stock intensity in this population density bin
346 well.

347 Additionally, we estimated lower and upper ranges for this catch-up and convergence scenario,
348 utilizing the 25th and 75th percentiles around the medians as density-dependent catch-up values, again
349 only for those cells of the bin which have stocks greater than zero. Percentiles were preferred as a
350 more robust measure over standard deviations, due to wide stock intensity distributions we found
351 over all cells of the bin, which are partially also due to local data errors or overlaps with water bodies
352 and mountainous regions. Finally, we ensured that national stock levels estimated for the year 2021
353 would not be reduced by the scenario nor its lower and upper range, meaning that if the scenario
354 resulted in lower national level stocks, we retained the baseline stock estimate also in the scenario;
355 which was the case most prominently for China, Russia and Malaysia.

356 3. Results

357 We present results on mobility infrastructure stocks globally and internationally for four income
358 groups for the year 2021 and explore global patterns of infrastructure stocks and their relation to
359 population density. We then show the material flows for maintenance and replacement of
360 infrastructure stocks, as well as the associated life cycle GHG emissions

361 3.1. Global and world-regional mobility infrastructure stocks

362 We find that the mass of global mobility infrastructures in ~2021 amounted to 313 Gt (Figure 2a). Most
363 of these material stocks (295 Gt) are in roads of various types (motorways, primary, secondary, tertiary,
364 local and rural roads) and their associated bridges and tunnels. Another 18 Gt are stocked in rail-based
365 infrastructure (railways, railway bridges and tunnels, subways, trams, and other rails) (Figure 2a). Due
366 to differing compositions of mobility infrastructure networks and their specific material construction
367 around the world, shares in the material stocks differ. In roads, this is mainly due to varying pavement
368 thickness and material composition. Consequently, motorways, for example, make up only 1.4% of the
369 global road network, but account for 12% of material stocks in roads (36 Gt). Despite their low material
370 intensity, the mass of local roads amounts to almost 124 Gt, i.e. 42% of road stocks. This is due to their
371 vastly greater network length, which amounts to 66% of all road kilometers. Railways and railway
372 bridges and tunnels account for the largest share in the global rail-based infrastructure stock,
373 accounting for almost 15 Gt (83%).

374 From a material perspective (Figure 2b), mobility infrastructure stocks are dominated by sand and
375 gravel, primarily used as sub-base layers and foundations. In roads, sand and gravel account for 69%
376 (203 Gt) of total stocks, followed by asphalt (25%, 73 Gt). In rail-based infrastructure, sand, gravel and
377 concrete are both dominant with 11 Gt (60%) and 5.8 Gt (31%) respectively, followed by iron/steel
378 with less than 1.3 Gt (7%). The large amounts of concrete in rail-based infrastructure can mainly be
379 attributed to concrete sleepers and railway as well as subway tunnels.

380

381 *Figure 2: Global mobility infrastructure networks, by type of infrastructure (a), by material (b), by income groups (c), and per*
 382 *capita material stocks as well as network length per capita (d). "Other materials" include aluminum and copper. "B+T" refers*
 383 *to bridges and tunnels. LI, LMI, UMI and HI refer to countries grouped as low-income, lower-middle income, upper-middle*
 384 *income and high income by World Bank.*

385 When considering the global distribution of mobility infrastructure stocks across world regions, we find
 386 a clear positive relation between income levels (GDP), infrastructure lengths and material stocks
 387 (Figure 2c&d). Lower income countries overall have a significantly lower share in global stocks and
 388 lower per capita stocks in general, both with regards to mass and network length. Almost 82% of all
 389 stocks are in upper-middle and high-income countries (Figure 2c), which make up a combined 59% of
 390 all countries. The other 41% of countries (low and lower-middle income countries) host the remaining
 391 infrastructures.

392 On a per capita level, we find global stocks of 45 t/cap (median) or 42 t/cap (average) with most
 393 countries lying within the interquartile (IQ) range between 23 t/cap (25th percentile) and 87 t/cap (75th

394 percentile) (Figure 3d). The population-weighted average of low-income countries is 19 t/cap with an
395 IQ ranging from 17 to 24 t/cap. Lower-middle income countries exhibit even lower per capita stocks
396 with a weighted average of 15 t/cap and an IQ ranging from 18 to 38 t/cap. The weighted average of
397 upper-middle income countries is 38 t/cap with an IQ ranging from 37 to 79 t/cap. Significantly larger
398 per capita stocks can be observed for high income countries, with a weighted average of 122 t/cap and
399 an IQ ranging from 69 to 149 t/cap. Niue ranks first in per capita stocks with 773 t/cap, followed by
400 Iceland with 496 t/cap, while Bangladesh comes in last with only 3.6 t/cap, highlighting the
401 considerable range in per capita stocks.

402 3.2. Mapping global patterns of mobility infrastructure stocks

403 We converted spatially explicit infrastructure networks as captured in OSM into a global gridded map
404 of material stocks, which allowed us to analyze patterns of total and per capita material stocks around
405 the world (Figure 3a). We find hotspots of material stocks of ~ 100.000 tons/km² in densely settled
406 cities around the world, especially in Europe, the USA, China, Japan, South Korea and India. We also
407 find intermediate stock densities of 1.000 – 20.000 tons/km² in many regions of the world, especially
408 in larger regions around cities and main settlement zones.

409 Interestingly, when mapping per-capita stocks, the picture partially reverses, and some hotspots of
410 material stocks per unit area turn into areas with only intermediate to relatively low levels of the
411 material stocks per capita of ~ 10 -100 tons/cap/km² (Figure 3b). This is most clearly visible in Europe,
412 India, and China, where relatively low material stocks per capita are sufficient even at high levels of
413 per-capita income, because areas with high population density can be serviced well with relatively little
414 mobility infrastructure per head of the population. On the other hand, in relatively sparsely settled
415 regions in high-income countries, we find high levels of infrastructure stocks per capita of ~ 5.000 –
416 50.000 tons/cap/area, most clearly visible for example in the USA and in Australia. At the same time,
417 we find that in most low to lower-middle income countries, stocks per area and stocks per capita are
418 very low except in highly dense and comparatively affluent urban areas.

419

420

421 *Figure 3: Global maps of mobility infrastructure stocks for the year 2021 at 5 arcmin resolution, showing a) total materials in*
422 *mobility infrastructure networks per square kilometer, and b) total stocks per capita per square kilometer. The*
423 *supplementary information also contains maps per disaggregated infrastructure types. Gridded population data for the year*
424 *2017 from HYDE 3.2.1. (Klein Goldewijk et al., 2017).*

425 The relationship between the spatial patterns and amounts of mobility infrastructure stocks versus the
426 human population utilizing them can also be investigated more systematically from these gridded
427 material stock maps (Figure 4; please note log and linear axis). We do find a relatively uniform relation
428 between higher population density and larger mobility infrastructure stocks, especially in high-income
429 and upper-middle income countries. We also find that higher national income levels are clearly
430 associated with higher stocks, compared to lower income levels at similar population densities (Figure
431 4, c.f. Figure 2d). In low income and lower-middle income countries, we also see that low to
432 intermediate population densities have consistently smaller material stocks. Only at the highest
433 population densities in relatively urban areas, do material stocks increase in an approximately
434 exponential manner, but remain considerably lower than in countries with higher income levels.

435

436 *Figure 4: Mobility infrastructure stocks and population density, for four global income groups. Due to the very wide spread*
 437 *of stock intensities at very low population densities, values for stock intensity per inhabitant are shown as logarithm (left*
 438 *hand axis), while the right hand axis is not. Gridded population data for the year 2017 from HYDE 3.2.1. (Klein Goldewijk et*
 439 *al., 2017). Please note that partial inclusion of water bodies or uninhabitable land, as well as small errors in OSM, can result*
 440 *in very low population densities having zero stock also.*

441 That stock levels vary substantially at the same level of population density indicates that differences in
 442 stock intensities are dependent on national income levels for similarly densely settled regions (Figure
 443 4). Especially in high-income regions we find median stocks of 94-140 kt/km² at the highest population
 444 densities above 3,000 cap/km². This effect is less pronounced for the upper-middle income regions
 445 and becomes very small in the lower income groups.

446 52% of global infrastructure stocks are found in regions with population densities below 100 cap/km²,
 447 with a large share of stocks (19%) present at population densities above 10 and below 50cap/km²
 448 (Figure 4e). Dominated by stocks in high and upper-middle income countries, the East coasts of USA
 449 and Brazil, as well as Western Europe and Western Russia contribute prominently to these high stock
 450 levels at this rather low population density.

451 3.3. Flows of materials, energy and emissions for stock expansion and maintenance

452 A first approximation of the ranges of material flows and life cycle emissions required to construct and
 453 maintain infrastructure material stocks can be derived from the estimated material stocks. For this
 454 purpose, we use low/intermediate/high variants for service lifetimes per material and infrastructure
 455 type, for infrastructure growth rates, and for life cycle emission factors (see methods section).

456 We estimate that 8.4 [5-13] Gt/year of materials are globally used to construct material stocks in
 457 mobility infrastructures, 66% of which are locked in for maintaining and replacing existing stocks
 458 (Figure 5a). Most of these materials are used in upper-middle and high-income countries (Figure 5c).
 459 Asphalt amounts to about half of these material flows, and sand and gravel for sub-base layers and
 460 foundations makes up for another third. Concrete, iron, steel and timber constitute a minor amount
 461 of material flows in mass units. Using low/high variants of lifetimes and infrastructure growth rates,
 462 we find a potential range of 5.4–12.7 Gt/year globally, with most of this range being due to the
 463 assumed ranges on network growth rates (Figure 5b). Interestingly, we find that infrastructure
 464 expansion only makes up 34% of these material flows across income groups and globally, while
 465 maintenance and replacement requirements become increasingly important at higher income levels.

466

467 *Figure 5: Material flows and life cycle GHG emissions due to mobility infrastructure maintenance and expansion, for global*
 468 *material flows (a), the contribution of the modelling parameters to the estimated uncertainty range (b), as well as material*
 469 *flows by income groups (c). Global cradle-to-gate life cycle emissions are shown in (d), with the contribution of the*
 470 *modelling parameters to the estimated uncertainty range (e), as well as the emissions by income group. The uncertainty*
 471 *ranges shown represent the combined effect of low-high assumptions on service lifetimes, infrastructure growth rates, as*

472 *well as life cycle emissions (see methods section). Other materials include aluminum, copper and other metals. NGR refers to*
473 *network growth rates, LT to lifetimes and LCE to life cycle emissions.*

474 Using world-regionalized life-cycle emissions data for materials production, we estimate that 369
475 MtCO₂eq/year are associated with the production of materials for build-up and maintenance of
476 mobility infrastructure stocks (Figure 6d). Production of asphalt (48%) and iron and steel (27%) are the
477 major causes of emissions, followed by concrete. Sand and gravel, while constituting 44% of the mass
478 flows, only causes a negligible amount of emissions (3%). Most emissions are due to materials
479 production in upper-middle and especially high-income countries (Figure 6f). Network expansion
480 causes ~30% of these emissions, while maintenance and replacement make up 70% of their emissions.

481

482 3.4. A population density scaled scenario of stock catch-up and convergence

483 Finally, we model how much materials and life cycle emissions would be required for an instantaneous
484 global catch-up of infrastructure stocks to levels found in high income countries at the same population
485 density (Figure 3), assuming that global population size and density remain constant (see methods
486 section). Note that this scenario does not represent a future trajectory nor realistic forecast, but rather
487 extrapolates the mass of stocks hypothetically needed at current population (density) numbers,
488 representing only a first explorative initial estimate.

489 We find that a global catch-up and convergence of mobility infrastructure stocks to those levels
490 currently found in high-income countries at the same population density per raster cell, would result
491 in a 1.4-fold increase of global infrastructure stocks to 429 Gt. This increase primarily occurs via roads
492 and specifically asphalt and aggregates (Figure 6a). For the low/high variant of catch-up stock levels
493 for the same population size and density, we find a range of 356-632 Gt of stocks. In the main scenario
494 reaching 429 Gt, stocks in low-income countries triple from 12 to 36 Gt (23 Gt increase) and more than
495 double in lower-middle income countries, from 44 to 94 Gt (50 Gt increase). Stocks in upper-middle
496 income countries grow by 40%, from 107 to 150 Gt (43 Gt increase). While relative increases are
497 highest in low-income and lower-middle income countries, the increase in upper-middle income
498 countries is comparable in absolute terms (Figure 6b). This catch-up scenario requires in total 117 [43-
499 319] Gt of material flows for expansion over current stocks, potentially causing 6.4 [2.6-19] Gt CO₂eq
500 at constant LCE factors (Figure 6c).

501

502 *Figure 6: A global infrastructure stocks catch-up and convergence scenario. Global stocks for 2021 and for the scenario (a),*
 503 *stock levels in the convergence scenario for each income region (b), material flows and emissions attached to the infrastructure*
 504 *expansion for global stock convergence (c), and annual material flows and life cycle emissions for the maintenance and*
 505 *replacement of the new stock level achieved in the catch-up scenario. Error bars show the modelled range resulting from low-*
 506 *intermediate-high assumptions on population density dependent stock catch-up levels, as well as lifetime assumptions by*
 507 *material and infrastructure type.*

508 Furthermore, such a population-density dependent globally equalized stock level would lock in annual
 509 material flows of 8.0 [5-17] Gt/year for maintenance and replacements, causing 0.43 [0.23-0.98] Gt
 510 CO₂eq/year, assuming constant life cycle emissions factors (Figure 6d). This would constitute an
 511 increase of 45% for materials flows and 42% for life cycle emissions locked in for maintaining already
 512 existing mobility infrastructure (Figure 5d).

513

514 4. Discussion

515 4.1. Mobility infrastructure stocks and flows and the global social metabolism

516 A number of country-level studies suggested that mobility infrastructure networks constitute a major
 517 share of total socio-economic material stocks and directly cause a large amount of flows associated to
 518 their construction and maintenance (Haberl et al., 2021b; Schiller et al., 2016; Tanikawa et al., 2015;
 519 Wiedenhofer et al., 2015). Additional flows are caused when the infrastructures are used by vehicles,
 520 trains or airplanes; these latter flows are outside the scope of this article. By drawing on previous
 521 inflow-driven “top-down” modelling of economy-wide material stocks and flows (Krausmann et al.,
 522 2017; Wiedenhofer et al., 2021), as well as international data sets on resource use and emissions
 523 (Friedlingstein et al., 2021; UNEP-IRP, 2022), we can, for the first time, assess the role of mobility stocks
 524 for the entire global socio-economic metabolism and all material stocks (Table 3).

525

526

527

528 *Table 3: The role of global mobility infrastructure for the global socio-economic metabolism. Please note that all numbers are*
 529 *rounded and therefore might not completely add up.*

	Material stocks	Material uses & extraction	Energy- and materials related GHG emissions	Sources
Mobility infrastructure	313 Gt, in 2021	8.4 [5.4-12.7] Gt/year	0.37 [0.2-0.6] Gt CO ₂ eq/year	This study
Maintenance and replacements		5.5 [4.0 - 7.0] Gt/year	0.26 [0.2-0.4] Gt CO ₂ eq/year	
Expansion		2.8 [1.4 - 5.7] Gt/year	0.10 [0.05-0.2] Gt CO ₂ eq/year	
Global economy-wide metabolism and total societal material stocks	1,064 Gt, in 2015	96.2 Gt/year, in 2019, all non-metallic minerals, ores, fossil fuels and biomass	36.3 Gt CO ₂ eq/year	(Friedlingstein et al., 2021; UNEP-IRP, 2022;
Non-metallic minerals	1,007 Gt, in 2015	44.8 Gt/year, in 2019, only non-metallic minerals		Wiedenhofer et al., 2021)
Share of mobility infrastructure stocks and flows in global metabolism	30-31% of global stocks	10% of total extraction 19% of non-metallics extraction	1% of global CO ₂ eq emissions	

530

531 We find that mobility infrastructure stocks make up ~30% of total material stocks, while our modelled
 532 material flows constitute ~10% of yearly total global resource extraction, as well as 19% of global non-
 533 metallic minerals use (Table 3). We find that ~6% of global resource extraction seems to be used for
 534 maintaining and replacing existing mobility infrastructure networks, which constitutes an important
 535 lock-in. The production of these materials, from a cradle-to-gate life-cycle assessment and excluding
 536 transport, construction and use, causes 1% of global GHG emissions; 70% of which are due to
 537 maintenance and replacements of existing infrastructure stocks (Table 3). While this might seem rather
 538 small, these emissions are equivalent to that of an entire high-income country like Italy.

539

540 **4.2. Future mobility infrastructure expansion and climate change mitigation**

541 There are substantial inequalities and insufficiencies in mobility infrastructures around the world, and
 542 their expansion and transformation will be required to achieve sustainable mobility and climate change
 543 mitigation (Lamb et al., 2021; Lowans et al., 2021).

544 We find that the hypothetical instantaneous global catch-up and convergence of infrastructure stock
 545 levels to those found in high income countries, could amount to 2.1 – 0.7% [6.5 – 0.3%] of the
 546 remaining 300 - 900 Gt CO₂ carbon budgets for limiting global heating to 1.5 – 2°C [both at 83%
 547 probability from the year 2020 onwards (IPCC, 2021)]. This is because the catch-up scenario requires
 548 117 [74-554] Gt of materials, causing 6.4 [2.6-19.4] GtCO₂eq of life cycle emissions, assuming constant
 549 LCE factors. Additionally, such a population-density scaled, globally equalized stock level would lock-in
 550 8.0 [4.7-16.8] Gt/year of maintenance and replacement material flows, causing 0.4 [0.23-1.0] Gt

551 CO₂eq/year, assuming constant LCE factors. Assuming that there are 20-40 years left for stabilizing
552 climate heating at 1.5-2°C and using constant LCE factors, maintenance and replacement related
553 emissions could hypothetically amount to 8-16 Gt CO₂eq, eating up another 5.3 – 0.9% of the
554 remaining carbon budgets. Depending on the stringency of climate heating targets and progress in
555 decarbonizing energy supply, the demand and size of the future stock and the resulting flows for
556 expansion, maintenance and replacements, mobility infrastructure stocks catch-up could in sum
557 require 1.6-7.4% of the remaining carbon budgets for 1.5-2°C, turning them into a substantial challenge
558 for climate change mitigation.

559 We also find that scaling the scenario with population-density substantially reduces estimates material
560 stocks and flows compared to simple but widespread scenarios using national averages. Using only
561 national per capita averages or medians for a catch-up and convergence scenario, we model an
562 increase of the global stock to 1,049-844 Gt, instead of the 429 [356-632] Gt presented herein.
563 Similarly, when using broader population density groupings, we estimate an increase of the global
564 stock to 522 [400-870] Gt for a catch-up and convergence. This clearly shows, in line with for example
565 (Wenz et al., 2020), that taking settlement patterns and the distribution of population and
566 infrastructures across the planet into account, makes a substantial difference for understanding and
567 modelling future resource use and infrastructure requirements. Future work should therefore develop
568 spatiotemporally explicit scenarios, linking changes in population size, density and settlement
569 patterns, as well as potential changes in infrastructure designs, compositions and life cycle emissions.

570 While our results suggest that infrastructure construction and maintenance itself poses a modest
571 challenge for climate-change mitigation, several caveats and important considerations remain. Most
572 importantly, herein we have not covered materials and emissions due to mobility itself, which the
573 infrastructure networks are enabling and locking in. Furthermore, the question arises if not much less
574 and different types of mobility infrastructure could also provide the physical basis for more equal and
575 sufficient access to sustainable mobility services required for high wellbeing for all (Virág et al., 2022;
576 Wenz et al., 2020). For example, providing a minimum level of infrastructures via quasi-universal access
577 to all-season roads would require investments of about USD 3 trillion, as well as cumulative emissions
578 from construction work until the end of the century of roughly 1-2 Gt of CO₂ (Wenz et al., 2020). It's
579 also unclear which spatial patterns of urbanization, land use and mobility are supported by these
580 infrastructures and which system-levels effects and lock-ins into specific mobility systems are
581 associated with them, e.g. car-based vs. focused on public transit (Mattioli et al., 2020; Seto et al.,
582 2016).

583 Finally, other environmental impacts of the substantial amount of resource use and infrastructure
584 network expansion should be addressed, such as the emerging 'tragedy of the sand commons' (Torres

585 et al., 2017), biodiversity impacts of non-metallic minerals and metal ores extraction (Luckeneder et
586 al., 2021; Torres et al., 2021; UNEP-IRP, 2019), or land use changes driven and enabled by
587 infrastructure expansion, as well as associated socio-economic impacts and benefits (Busch and
588 Ferretti-Gallon, 2020; Vilela et al., 2020).

589 4.3. Robustness, limitations and next steps

590 Any global modelling and mapping necessarily has limitations and requires some simplifications and
591 assumptions. We do find that our stock estimates presented herein are in good agreement with most
592 of the comparable literature (see supplementary information section 1). Still, several limitations and
593 potential next steps remain.

594 Firstly, while OSM has been evaluated as more than 80% complete in its coverage of mobility
595 infrastructures, it does often lack information on specific classes and their attributes; it is also not
596 globally harmonized nor a quality ensured data product (Barrington-Leigh and Millard-Ball, 2017;
597 Meijer et al., 2018). The completeness of OSM maps is shaped by internet access and open governance
598 structures encouraging crowd-sourcing information; additionally, very densely and very sparsely
599 settled areas seem to be relatively more complete (Barrington-Leigh and Millard-Ball, 2017). Because
600 comparisons of official network data as well as GRIP4 data versus OSM show substantial gaps and
601 sometimes complete omissions in official data, especially for lower order road infrastructure such as
602 residential/local/rural roads (see supplementary information and (Haberl et al., 2021b; Meijer et al.,
603 2018)), we do still utilize OSM. However, crowd-sourced data have limitations, as classifications of
604 infrastructure are not fully consistent across countries or regions because data quality depends on the
605 users to input descriptive data, necessitating broader grouping and assumptions when allocating
606 detailed OSM classes to material compositions. Furthermore, OSM lacks age-class cohort information,
607 prohibiting proper dynamic modelling of stock-flow relations. Applying the quality improving and
608 harmonizing procedures developed by (Meijer et al., 2018), as well as combining OSM with historical
609 sources and maps therefore constitute valuable next steps for understanding the development of
610 infrastructure networks around the world (Uhl et al., 2022).

611 Secondly, the material intensities and infrastructure design parameters were compiled from various
612 sources, but due to relatively little useful data we decided for globally “typical” material intensities per
613 infrastructure type for the majority of the world, as country-specific information was only available for
614 a handful of countries (see methods section, Table 1 and supplementary data). Most of this
615 information is drawn from national standards and construction manuals, suggesting that the estimates
616 constitute the “minimum” material composition and widths, as legislated. Actual on-site material
617 stocks and flows additionally depend on a range of factors, such as local soil conditions, detailed local
618 construction plans, historical societal circumstances, regularly occurring widening of existing roads

619 esp. in high income countries, government budget constraints and priorities, as well as actual
620 compliance of construction companies with standards and regulations (Ebrahimi et al., 2022;
621 Grossegger, 2022; Kloostra et al., 2022; Miatto et al., 2017).

622 Thirdly, we also do not cover the following mobility infrastructures and related buildings which could
623 amount to substantial stock also, primarily due to a lack of global data: starting from parking lots, to
624 ports, as well as all buildings directly used and required to utilize mobility infrastructures, e.g., parking
625 garages, railway stations, gas stations, airport and port buildings as well as depots or facilities.
626 Furthermore, technical components such as lighting systems and traffic lights for roads, railways and
627 other infrastructure, electrical power supply systems for railways, ventilation devices in tunnels, poles,
628 safety fences and noise protection walls for roads, etc. are all excluded due to a lack of data. Clearly,
629 more stratified and internationally representative information on infrastructure extents, types, design
630 parameters, construction types and material compositions would be desirable for future research and
631 would most likely increase all estimates presented herein.

632 Fourthly, while we do cover the major 'cradle-to-gate' life-cycle phases of materials extraction,
633 production, recycling contents and energy supply, we do exclude transport of materials, construction
634 activities, use and recycling phases. Life-cycle factors for final energy use and GHG emissions depend
635 on LCA data from inconsistent system boundaries, varying scopes and often incomplete reporting and
636 documentation (Hellweg and Canals, 2014). As common in LCA, aspects such as local transport of
637 materials, construction activity itself, as well as energy and emissions during material recovery
638 activities were excluded, as they usually contribute only a minor share to overall life cycle emissions
639 (Hoxha et al., 2021; Jiang and Wu, 2019; Olugbenga et al., 2019). Regarding recycling, herein we limited
640 the scope of life cycle GHG emissions from secondary material use to industrial processes and do not
641 include demolition and material collection itself. The influence of these life-cycle phases are usually
642 considered negligible for those materials with high recycling and re-use rates (asphalt, steel, aluminum,
643 copper), and are generally dependent on the specific context, such as average transport distances
644 (AzariJafari et al., 2021; Hoxha et al., 2021; Olugbenga et al., 2019). For aggregates, we assume that
645 secondary materials are associated with the same energy and GHG intensities as natural aggregates,
646 as literature data indicate similar ranges and is rather inconclusive as to whether recycled or natural
647 aggregates have lower life cycle energy use and emissions (Hossain et al., 2016; Hoxha et al., 2021;
648 Marinković et al., 2010; Olugbenga et al., 2019). In summary, more holistic coverage of all life cycle
649 stages, different types of construction, incl. clearing of previous land-uses, would be desirable (Saxe
650 and Kasraian, 2020). While we do cover most of the life cycle emissions associated with mobility
651 infrastructures, adding more detailed information would most likely increase the presented GHG
652 emissions estimates.

653 Finally, we also do not fully cover the use phase of infrastructure stocks, i.e. traffic emissions which
654 amount to 15% of global GHG emissions (Lamb et al., 2021), as well as carbonation of concrete during
655 use over many decades and especially at the end-of-life phase (Xi et al., 2016). We also do note that
656 the concrete contents of global infrastructure might be underestimated herein, due to the lack of
657 information on the shares of concrete vs asphalt roads across most countries. Carbonation is then
658 characterized by numerous influencing parameters, such as the sizes and geometrical shapes of
659 concrete elements, the surface area exposed to air, demolition, storage and recycling practices. Studies
660 suggest that carbonation can have substantial effects on the overall life-cycle emissions net balance of
661 concrete, especially if the demolition and end-of-life stages are included and very long time periods
662 are assessed (AzariJafari et al., 2021; Butera et al., 2015; Xi et al., 2016). It was however also suggested
663 that concrete of the highest strength classes is typically used for pavements and infrastructures (Pade
664 and Guimaraes, 2007), which is characterized by particularly low carbonation rates during the use
665 phase. Future work should therefore address the use phase of infrastructure stocks more
666 comprehensively and over long time periods.

667

668 5. Concluding remarks

669 We present the first comprehensive global mapping and modelling of mobility infrastructure stocks
670 and associated flows of material and life cycle emissions, aiming to understand the biophysical basis
671 of mobility services. We found an accumulated material stock of 313 Gt in 2021, which amounts to
672 ~1/3 of global economy-wide material stocks of all buildings, infrastructure and machinery. We find
673 substantial global and spatial inequality in infrastructure stocks, with clear relations between both
674 population density and national income levels (GDP) jointly shaping infrastructure stock levels.

675 The modelled material flows for expansion and maintenance, ~8.4 Gt/year, amount to ~10% of global
676 resource extraction, indicating substantial environmental pressures during resource extraction and
677 materials processing, infrastructure construction, as well as maintenance and replacements. The
678 associated life cycle emissions amount to 0.37 Gt CO₂-eq/year, approx. 1% of global energy-related
679 GHG emissions. We also find that ~2/3 of these material flows and emissions are due to maintenance
680 and replacements of existing infrastructure stocks, constituting an important lock-in. Depending the
681 assumptions for future stock expansion in a hypothetical catch-up and convergence scenario, we do
682 find that the resulting material flows and associated life cycle emissions could become a substantial
683 challenge for climate change mitigation, requiring 117 [43-319] Gt of materials flows and 6.4 [2.6-19]
684 Gt of emissions, locking in 8 [5-17] and 0.4 [0.2-1] Gt/year of materials and emissions for future
685 maintenance. This future stock expansion and maintenance could require 1.6-7.4% of the carbon
686 budgets for stabilizing climate heating at 1.5-2°C [83% probability from 2020 on (IPCC, 2021)].

687 While sufficient mobility infrastructures and safe as well as affordable mobility services for everyone
688 are clearly required, transforming them into climate-neutral and resource-efficient modes is of crucial
689 importance, as policymakers and stakeholders aim to reduce GHG emissions fast enough to mitigate
690 rapidly progressing climate heating. Infrastructures are a pivotal leverage point for climate change
691 mitigation and resource efficiency, as they constitute materialized long-term path dependencies.
692 Supply- and demand-side measures seem necessary to achieve such a transformation of mobility
693 infrastructures which are currently dominated by roads. These measures should aim to replace and
694 build much more resource-efficient infrastructure networks where they are needed, as well as
695 mitigating the demand for more infrastructure and mobility itself.

696

6. References

- 698 Alzaim, M., Gedik, A., Lav, A.H., 2020. Effect of Modulus of Bituminous Layers and Utilization of Capping
699 Layer on Weak Pavement Subgrades. *Civ. Eng. J.* 6, 1286–1299. [https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-](https://doi.org/10.28991/cej-2020-03091548)
700 2020-03091548
- 701 Alzard, M.H., Maraqa, M.A., Chowdhury, R., Khan, Q., Albuquerque, F.D.B., Mauga, T.I., Aljunadi, K.N.,
702 2019. Estimation of Greenhouse Gas Emissions Produced by Road Projects in Abu Dhabi,
703 United Arab Emirates. *Sustainability* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11082367>
- 704 AzariJafari, H., Guo, F., Gregory, J., Kirchain, R., 2021. Carbon uptake of concrete in the US pavement
705 network. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 167, 105397.
706 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105397>
- 707 AzariJafari, H., Yahia, A., Ben Amor, M., 2016. Life cycle assessment of pavements: reviewing research
708 challenges and opportunities. *J. Clean. Prod.* 112, 2187–2197.
709 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.09.080>
- 710 Bai, J., Qu, J., Maraseni, T.N., Wu, J., Xu, L., Fan, Y., 2019. Spatial and Temporal Variations of Embodied
711 Carbon Emissions in China's Infrastructure. *Sustainability* 11.
712 <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11030749>
- 713 Barrington-Leigh, C., Millard-Ball, A., 2017. The world's user-generated road map is more than 80%
714 complete. *PLOS ONE* 12, e0180698. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0180698>
- 715 Busch, J., Ferretti-Gallon, K., 2020. What Drives Deforestation and What Stops It? A Meta-Analysis. *Rev.*
716 *Environ. Econ. Policy.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/reep/rew013>
- 717 Butera, S., Christensen, T.H., Astrup, T.F., 2015. Life cycle assessment of construction and demolition
718 waste management. *Waste Manag.* 44, 196–205.
719 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2015.07.011>
- 720 Chen, J., Zhao, F., Liu, Z., Ou, X., Hao, H., 2017. Greenhouse gas emissions from road construction in
721 China: A province-level analysis. *J. Clean. Prod.* 168, 1039–1047.
722 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.08.243>
- 723 Creutzig, F., Callaghan, M., Ramakrishnan, A., Javaid, A., Niamir, L., Minx, J., Müller-Hansen, F.,
724 Sovacool, B., Afroz, Z., Andor, M., Antal, M., Court, V., Das, N., Díaz-José, J., Döbbe, F., Figueroa,
725 M.J., Gouldson, A., Haberl, H., Hook, A., Ivanova, D., Lamb, W.F., Maïzi, N., Mata, É., Nielsen,
726 K.S., Onyige, C.D., Reisch, L.A., Roy, J., Scheelbeek, P., Sethi, M., Some, S., Sorrell, S., Tessier,
727 M., Urmee, T., Virág, D., Wan, C., Wiedenhofer, D., Wilson, C., 2021. Reviewing the scope and
728 thematic focus of 100 000 publications on energy consumption, services and social aspects of
729 climate change: a big data approach to demand-side mitigation *. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16,
730 033001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abd78b>
- 731 CSIR, 2000. Guidelines for human settlement planning and design: The red book, Volume 1 & 2. Council
732 for Scientific and Industrial Research.
- 733 DMR, 2014. Pavement Design Guidelines (Flexible Pavement). Department of Roads, Ministry of
734 Physical Infrastructure and Transport, Government of Nepal, Kathmandu, Nepal.
- 735 DMT, 2016. Pavement Design Manual (No. TR-513). Department of Municipal Affairs and Transport,
736 Government of Abu Dhabi, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates.
- 737 Ebrahimi, B., Rosado, L., Wallbaum, H., 2022. Machine learning-based stocks and flows modeling of
738 road infrastructure. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 26, 44–57. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13232>
- 739 European Commission, 2020. EU Transport in Figures 2020. Statistical Pocketbook, Mobility and
740 Transport. Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- 741 European Commission. Joint Research Centre, 2019. The future of road transport : implications of
742 automated, connected, low-carbon and shared mobility, EUR (Luxembourg. Online).
743 Publications Office, LU.
- 744 Eurostat, 2021a. Length of other roads by category of roads [WWW Document]. URL
745 https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=road_if_roadsc&lang=en
- 746 Eurostat, 2021b. Railway transport - length of tracks [WWW Document]. URL
747 https://appsso.eurostat.ec.europa.eu/nui/show.do?dataset=rail_if_tracks&lang=en

748 Federal Aviation Administration, 2016. 150/5320-6F - Airport Pavement Design and Evaluation.
749 Advisory Circular.

750 Fisch-Romito, V., 2021. Embodied carbon dioxide emissions to provide high access levels to basic
751 infrastructure around the world. *Glob. Environ. Change* 70, 102362.
752 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102362>

753 Fishman, T., Wiedenhofer, D., Frantz, D., Guo, J., Liu, Z., Schug, F., Peled, Y., Baumgart, A., Tanikawa,
754 H., Haberl, H., in preparation. Which method for which case? A comparative application of four
755 approaches to mapping material stocks of buildings and infrastructures in Japan.

756 Frantz, D., Schug, F., Wiedenhofer, D., Baumgart, A., Virág, D., Cooper, S., Gomez-Medina, C., Lehmann,
757 F., Udelhoven, T., van der Linden, S., Hostert, P., Haberl, H., submitted. Weighing the US
758 Economy: Map of Built Structures Unveils Patterns in Human-Dominated Landscapes.

759 Friedlingstein, P., Jones, M.W., O'Sullivan, M., Andrew, R.M., Bakker, D.C.E., Hauck, J., Le Quéré, C.,
760 Peters, G.P., Peters, W., Pongratz, J., Sitch, S., Canadell, J.G., Ciais, P., Jackson, R.B., Alin, S.R.,
761 Anthoni, P., Bates, N.R., Becker, M., Bellouin, N., Bopp, L., Chau, T.T.T., Chevallier, F., Chini,
762 L.P., Cronin, M., Currie, K.I., Decharme, B., Djeutchouang, L., Dou, X., Evans, W., Feely, R.A.,
763 Feng, L., Gasser, T., Gilfillan, D., Gkritzalis, T., Grassi, G., Gregor, L., Gruber, N., Gürses, Ö.,
764 Harris, I., Houghton, R.A., Hurtt, G.C., Iida, Y., Ilyina, T., Luijkx, I.T., Jain, A.K., Jones, S.D., Kato,
765 E., Kennedy, D., Klein Goldewijk, K., Knauer, J., Korsbakken, J.I., Körtzinger, A., Landschützer,
766 P., Lauvset, S.K., Lefèvre, N., Lienert, S., Liu, J., Marland, G., McGuire, P.C., Melton, J.R., Munro,
767 D.R., Nabel, J.E.M.S., Nakaoka, S.-I., Niwa, Y., Ono, T., Pierrot, D., Poulter, B., Rehder, G.,
768 Resplandy, L., Robertson, E., Rödenbeck, C., Rosan, T.M., Schwinger, J., Schwingshackl, C.,
769 Séférian, R., Sutton, A.J., Sweeney, C., Tanhua, T., Tans, P.P., Tian, H., Tilbrook, B., Tubiello, F.,
770 van der Werf, G., Vuichard, N., Wada, C., Wanninkhof, R., Watson, A., Willis, D., Wiltshire, A.J.,
771 Yuan, W., Yue, C., Yue, X., Zaehle, S., Zeng, J., 2021. Global Carbon Budget 2021 (preprint).
772 *Antroposphere – Energy and Emissions*. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2021-386>

773 Fu, C., Zhang, Y., Deng, T., Daigo, I., 2021. The evolution of material stock research: From exploring to
774 rising to hot studies. *J. Ind. Ecol. jiec.13195*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13195>

775 Gassner, A., Lederer, J., Fellner, J., 2020. Material stock development of the transport sector in the city
776 of Vienna. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 24, 1364–1378. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13024>

777 Geofabrik, 2022. Open Street Maps Data Extract [WWW Document]. URL <http://www.geofabrik.de>
778 (accessed 8.31.21).

779 Grossegger, D., 2022. Material flow analysis study of asphalt in an Austrian municipality. *J. Ind. Ecol.*
780 26, 996–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13243>

781 Guo, Z., Hu, D., Zhang, F., Huang, G., Xiao, Q., 2014. An integrated material metabolism model for
782 stocks of urban road system in Beijing, China. *Sci. Total Environ.* 470–471, 883–894.
783 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.10.041>

784 Haberl, H., Dominik Wiedenhofer, Karl-Heinz Erb, Christoph Görg, Fridolin Krausmann, 2017. The
785 Material Stock–Flow–Service Nexus: A New Approach for Tackling the Decoupling Conundrum.
786 *Sustainability* 9, 1049. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9071049>

787 Haberl, H., Schmid, M., Haas, W., Wiedenhofer, D., Rau, H., Winiwarter, V., 2021a. Stocks, flows,
788 services and practices: Nexus approaches to sustainable social metabolism. *Ecol. Econ.* 182,
789 106949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.106949>

790 Haberl, H., Wiedenhofer, D., Pauliuk, S., Krausmann, F., Müller, D.B., Fischer-Kowalski, M., 2019.
791 Contributions of sociometabolic research to sustainability science. *Nat. Sustain.* 2, 173–184.
792 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0225-2>

793 Haberl, H., Wiedenhofer, D., Schug, F., Frantz, D., Virág, D., Plutzar, C., Gruhler, K., Lederer, J., Schiller,
794 G., Fishman, T., Lanau, M., Gattringer, A., Kemper, T., Liu, G., Tanikawa, H., van der Linden, S.,
795 Hostert, P., 2021b. High-Resolution Maps of Material Stocks in Buildings and Infrastructures in
796 Austria and Germany. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* [acs.est.0c05642](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c05642).
797 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c05642>

798 Hellweg, S., Canals, L.M. i, 2014. Emerging approaches, challenges and opportunities in life cycle
799 assessment. *Science* 344, 1109–1113. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1248361>

800 Henderson, M., van Zyl, G., 2017. Management of unpaved roads : developing a strategy and refining
801 models. Presented at the 36th Annual Southern African Transport Conference, CSIR
802 International Convention Centre, Pretoria, South Africa.

803 Hertwich, E.G., 2021. Increased carbon footprint of materials production driven by rise in investments.
804 Nat. Geosci. 14, 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-021-00690-8>

805 Hossain, Md.U., Poon, C.S., Lo, I.M.C., Cheng, J.C.P., 2016. Comparative environmental evaluation of
806 aggregate production from recycled waste materials and virgin sources by LCA. Resour.
807 Conserv. Recycl. 109, 67–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.02.009>

808 Hoxha, E., Vignisdottir, H.R., Barbieri, D.M., Wang, F., Bohne, R.A., Kristensen, T., Passer, A., 2021. Life
809 cycle assessment of roads: Exploring research trends and harmonization challenges. Sci. Total
810 Environ. 759, 143506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143506>

811 IPCC, 2021. Climate change 2021 : the physical science basis : Working Group I contribution to the sixth
812 assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on climate change [Masson-Delmotte, V.,
813 P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M.
814 Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu,
815 and B. Zhou (eds.)]. [WWW Document]. URL
816 https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/downloads/report/IPCC_AR6_WGI_Full_Report.pdf

817 Jeyaseelan, T., Ekambaram, P., Subramanian, J., Shamim, T., 2022. A comprehensive review on the
818 current trends, challenges and future prospects for sustainable mobility. Renew. Sustain.
819 Energy Rev. 157, 112073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2022.112073>

820 Jiang, R., Wu, P., 2019. Estimation of environmental impacts of roads through life cycle assessment: A
821 critical review and future directions. Transp. Res. Part Transp. Environ. 77, 148–163.
822 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2019.10.010>

823 Klein Goldewijk, K., Beusen, A., Doelman, J., Stehfest, E., 2017. Anthropogenic land use estimates for
824 the Holocene – HYDE 3.2. Earth Syst. Sci. Data 9, 927–953. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-927-2017>

825

826 Kloostra, B., Makarchuk, B., Saxe, S., 2022. Bottom-up estimation of material stocks and flows in
827 Toronto’s road network. J. Ind. Ecol. n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13229>

828 Krausmann, F., Wiedenhofer, D., Haberl, H., 2020. Growing stocks of buildings, infrastructures and
829 machinery as key challenge for compliance with climate targets. Glob. Environ. Change 61,
830 102034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102034>

831 Krausmann, F., Wiedenhofer, D., Lauk, C., Haas, W., Tanikawa, H., Fishman, T., Miatto, A., Schandl, H.,
832 Haberl, H., 2017. Global socioeconomic material stocks rise 23-fold over the 20th century and
833 require half of annual resource use. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. 114, 1880–1885.
834 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1613773114>

835 Lamb, W.F., Wiedmann, T., Pongratz, J., Andrew, R., Crippa, M., Olivier, J.G.J., Wiedenhofer, D.,
836 Mattioli, G., Al Khouradje, A., House, J., Pachauri, S., Figueroa, M., Saheb, Y., Slade, R.,
837 Hubacek, K., Sun, L., Ribeiro, S.K., Khennas, S., de la Rue du Can, S., Chapungu, L., Davis, S.J.,
838 Bashmakov, I., Dai, H., Dhakal, S., Tan, X., Geng, Y., Gu, B., Minx, J.C., 2021. A review of trends
839 and drivers of greenhouse gas emissions by sector from 1990 to 2018. Environ. Res. Lett.
840 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abee4e>

841 Lanau, M., Liu, G., 2020. Developing an Urban Resource Cadaster for Circular Economy: A Case of
842 Odense, Denmark. Environ. Sci. Technol. 54, 4675–4685.
843 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b07749>

844 Lanau, M., Liu, G., Kral, U., Wiedenhofer, D., Keijzer, E.E.E., Yu, C., Ehlert, C., 2019. Taking stock of built
845 environment stock studies: Progress and prospects. Environ. Sci. Technol. acs.est.8b06652.
846 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b06652>

847 Lin, C., Liu, G., Müller, D.B., 2017. Characterizing the role of built environment stocks in human
848 development and emission growth. Resour. Conserv. Recycl.
849 doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.07.004. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.07.004>

- 850 Lowans, C., Furszyfer Del Rio, D., Sovacool, B.K., Rooney, D., Foley, A.M., 2021. What is the state of the
851 art in energy and transport poverty metrics? A critical and comprehensive review. *Energy Econ.*
852 101, 105360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2021.105360>
- 853 Luckeneder, S., Giljum, S., Schaffartzik, A., Maus, V., Tost, M., 2021. Surge in global metal mining
854 threatens vulnerable ecosystems. *Glob. Environ. Change* 69, 102303.
855 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102303>
- 856 Mao, R., Bao, Y., Duan, H., Liu, G., 2021. Global urban subway development, construction material
857 stocks, and embodied carbon emissions. *Humanit. Soc. Sci. Commun.* 8, 83.
858 <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00757-2>
- 859 Marinković, S., Radonjanin, V., Malešev, M., Ignjatović, I., 2010. Comparative environmental
860 assessment of natural and recycled aggregate concrete. *Waste Manag.* 30, 2255–2264.
861 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2010.04.012>
- 862 Mattioli, G., Roberts, C., Steinberger, J.K., Brown, A., 2020. The political economy of car dependence:
863 A systems of provision approach. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 66, 101486.
864 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101486>
- 865 Meijer, J.R., Huijbregts, M.A.J., Schotten, K.C.G.J., Schipper, A.M., 2018. Global patterns of current and
866 future road infrastructure. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 13, 064006. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aabd42>
- 867
- 868 Miatto, A., Dawson, D., Nguyen, P.D., Kanaoka, K.S., Tanikawa, H., 2021. The urbanisation–environment
869 conflict: Insights from material stock and productivity of transport infrastructure in Hanoi,
870 Vietnam. *J. Environ. Manage.* 294, 113007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.113007>
- 871 Miatto, A., Schandl, H., Wiedenhofer, D., Krausmann, F., Tanikawa, H., 2017. Modeling material flows
872 and stocks of the road network in the United States 1905–2015. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 127,
873 168–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.08.024>
- 874 Moran, D., Giljum, S., Kanemoto, K., Godar, J., 2020. From Satellite to Supply Chain: New Approaches
875 Connect Earth Observation to Economic Decisions. *One Earth* 3, 5–8.
876 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.06.007>
- 877 Müller, D.B., Liu, G., Løvik, A.N., Modaresi, R., Pauliuk, S., Steinhoff, F.S., Brattebø, H., 2013. Carbon
878 Emissions of Infrastructure Development. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47, 11739–11746.
879 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es402618m>
- 880 Nguyen, T.C., Fishman, T., Miatto, A., Tanikawa, H., 2018. Estimating the Material Stock of Roads: The
881 Vietnamese Case Study: The Vietnamese Case Study. *J. Ind. Ecol.*
882 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12773>
- 883 Noll, D., Wiedenhofer, D., Miatto, A., Singh, S.J., 2019. The expansion of the built environment, waste
884 generation and EU recycling targets on Samothraki, Greece: An island's dilemma. *Resour.*
885 *Conserv. Recycl.* 150, 104405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2019.104405>
- 886 OECD, 2021. Detailed annual transport statistics: Road-Infrastructure [WWW Document]. URL
887 <https://stats.oecd.org/Index.aspx?QueryId=97817>
- 888 Olugbenga, O., Kalyviotis, N., Saxe, S., 2019. Embodied emissions in rail infrastructure: a critical
889 literature review. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14, 123002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab442f>
- 890 OurAirports, 2021. Open data downloads [WWW Document]. URL <https://ourairports.com/data/>
- 891 Özgenel, M., 2016. Rural arterial road planning and design steps (Session 12: Roads: Planning, Design
892 and Construction Issues). Presented at the International Conference on Traffic and Transport
893 Engineering, Belgrade, Serbia, pp. 663–669.
- 894 Pade, C., Guimaraes, M., 2007. The CO₂ uptake of concrete in a 100 year perspective. *Cem. Concr. Res.*
895 37, 1348–1356. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cemconres.2007.06.009>
- 896 Pauliuk, S., Hertwich, E.G., 2015. Socioeconomic metabolism as paradigm for studying the biophysical
897 basis of human societies. *Ecol. Econ.* 119, 83–93.
898 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2015.08.012>
- 899 Saxe, S., Kasraian, D., 2020. Rethinking environmental LCA life stages for transport infrastructure to
900 facilitate holistic assessment. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 24, 1031–1046. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.13010>

901 Schiller, G., Müller, F., Ortlepp, R., 2016. Mapping the anthropogenic stock in Germany: Metabolic
902 evidence for a circular economy. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* in press, doi:
903 10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.08.007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2016.08.007>

904 Seto, K.C., Davis, S.J., Mitchell, R.B., Stokes, E.C., Unruh, G., Ürge-Vorsatz, D., 2016. Carbon Lock-In:
905 Types, Causes, and Policy Implications. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 41, 425–452.
906 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-110615-085934>

907 Tanikawa, H., Fishman, T., Hashimoto, S., Daigo, I., Oguchi, M., Miatto, A., Takagi, S., Yamashita, N.,
908 Schandl, H., 2021. A framework of indicators for associating material stocks and flows to
909 service provisioning: Application for Japan 1990–2015. *J. Clean. Prod.* 285, 125450.
910 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.125450>

911 Tanikawa, H., Fishman, T., Okuoka, K., Sugimoto, K., 2015. The Weight of Society Over Time and Space:
912 A Comprehensive Account of the Construction Material Stock of Japan, 1945–2010. *J. Ind. Ecol.*
913 19, 778–791. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12284>

914 Torres, A., Brandt, J., Lear, K., Liu, J., 2017. A looming tragedy of the sand commons. *Science* 357, 970–
915 971. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa0503>

916 Torres, A., Simoni, M.U., Keiding, J.K., Müller, D.B., zu Ermgassen, S.O.S.E., Liu, J., Jaeger, J.A.G., Winter,
917 M., Lambin, E.F., 2021. Sustainability of the global sand system in the Anthropocene. *One Earth*
918 4, 639–650. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2021.04.011>

919 Uhl, J.H., Leyk, S., Chiang, Y.-Y., Knoblock, C.A., 2022. Towards the automated large-scale
920 reconstruction of past road networks from historical maps. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* 94,
921 101794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2022.101794>

922 UIC, 2016. Carbon footprint of railway infrastructure. Comparing existing methodologies on typical
923 corridors. Recommendations for harmonized approach. International Union of Railways, Paris.

924 UNECE, 2021a. Total length of roads at 31 December by type of road. UNECE Transport Division
925 Database [WWW Document]. URL
926 [https://w3.unece.org/PXWeb2015/pxweb/en/STAT/STAT__40-TRTRANS__11-
927 TRINFRA/ZZZ_en_TRInfraRoad_r.px/](https://w3.unece.org/PXWeb2015/pxweb/en/STAT/STAT__40-TRTRANS__11-TRINFRA/ZZZ_en_TRInfraRoad_r.px/)

928 UNECE, 2021b. Total length of lines operated (km) at 31 December by type of track. UNECE Transport
929 Division Database [WWW Document]. URL
930 [https://w3.unece.org/PXWeb2015/pxweb/en/STAT/STAT__40-TRTRANS__11-
931 TRINFRA/ZZZ_en_TRRailInfra1_r.px/](https://w3.unece.org/PXWeb2015/pxweb/en/STAT/STAT__40-TRTRANS__11-TRINFRA/ZZZ_en_TRRailInfra1_r.px/)

932 UNEP-IRP, 2022. Global Material Flows Database.

933 UNEP-IRP, 2019. Global Resources Outlook 2019. Natural resources for the future we want. United
934 Nations Environment Programme, Nairobi, Kenya.

935 van der Voet, E., Kleijn, R., Huele, R., Ishikawa, M., Verkuijlen, E., 2002. Predicting future emissions
936 based on characteristics of stocks. *Ecol. Econ.* 41, 223–234. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-
937 8009\(02\)00028-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-8009(02)00028-9)

938 Vilela, T., Malky Harb, A., Bruner, A., Laísa da Silva Arruda, V., Ribeiro, V., Auxiliadora Costa Alencar, A.,
939 Julissa Escobedo Grandez, A., Rojas, A., Laina, A., Botero, R., 2020. A better Amazon road
940 network for people and the environment. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 117, 7095–7102.
941 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1910853117>

942 Virág, D., Wiedenhofer, D., Baumgart, A., Matej, S., Krausmann, F., Min, J., Rao, N.D., Haberl, H., 2022.
943 How much infrastructure is required to support decent mobility for all? An exploratory
944 assessment. *Ecol. Econ.* 200, 107511. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107511>

945 Virág, D., Wiedenhofer, D., Haas, W., Haberl, H., Kalt, G., Krausmann, F., 2021. The stock-flow-service
946 nexus of personal mobility in an urban context: Vienna, Austria. *Environ. Dev.* 100628.
947 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2021.100628>

948 Watt, H., 2019. Benchmarking embodied carbon of highway bridges. MEng Dissertation Thesis.
949 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom.

950 Wenz, L., Weddige, U., Jakob, M., Steckel, J.C., 2020. Road to glory or highway to hell? Global road
951 access and climate change mitigation. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 15, 075010.
952 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ab858d>

- 953 Wiedenhofer, D., Drewniok, M.P., Frantz, D., Gauch, H., Lanau, M., Schug, F., Serrenho, A.C., Tingley,
954 D.D., Baumgart, A., Virág, D., Watt, H., Haberl, H., in preparation. High-resolution mapping of
955 material stocks of buildings and infrastructure in the United Kingdom and Republic of Ireland.
956 Wiedenhofer, D., Fishman, T., Plank, B., Miatto, A., Lauk, C., Haas, W., Haberl, H., Krausmann, F., 2021.
957 Prospects for a saturation of humanity's resource use? An analysis of material stocks and flows
958 in nine world regions from 1900 to 2035. *Glob. Environ. Change* 71, 102410.
959 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102410>
960 Wiedenhofer, D., Steinberger, J.K., Eisenmenger, N., Haas, W., 2015. Maintenance and Expansion:
961 Modeling Material Stocks and Flows for Residential Buildings and Transportation Networks in
962 the EU25. *J. Ind. Ecol.* 19, 538–551. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jiec.12216>
963 World Bank, 2021. The World by Income and Region [WWW Document]. URL
964 [https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/the-world-by-income-and-](https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/the-world-by-income-and-region.html)
965 [region.html](https://datatopics.worldbank.org/world-development-indicators/the-world-by-income-and-region.html)
966 Xi, F., Davis, S.J., Ciais, P., Crawford-Brown, D., Guan, D., Pade, C., Shi, T., Syddall, M., Lv, J., Ji, L., Bing,
967 L., Wang, J., Wei, W., Yang, K.-H., Lagerblad, B., Galan, I., Andrade, C., Zhang, Y., Liu, Z., 2016.
968 Substantial global carbon uptake by cement carbonation. *Nat. Geosci.* 9, 880–883.
969 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2840>
970
971